

PURCHASE DECISIONS ACEH CAKE UMKM

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Received : 01 March 2026

Accepted : 30 March 2026

Revised : 10 March 2026

Published : 15 April 2026

Abstract

This study aims to test and analyze the influence of promotion through TikTok and product innovation on purchasing decisions in micro, small, and medium enterprises of Acehese Traditional Cakes. The determination of the research sample uses the Purba formula. The sample used in this study was 96 consumers in micro, small, and medium enterprises of Acehese Traditional Cakes who were willing to be respondents. The analytical method applied was multiple linear regression analysis. The results of the study indicate that promotion through TikTok partially has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions in micro, small, and medium enterprises of Acehese Traditional Cakes in Banda Aceh city. Product innovation partially has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions in micro, small, and medium enterprises of Acehese Traditional Cakes in Banda Aceh city. Promotion through TikTok and product innovation simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions in micro, small, and medium enterprises of Acehese Traditional Cakes in Banda Aceh city.

Keywords: *Promotion Through TikTok, Product Innovation, Purchasing Decisions*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Digital marketing is a strategy for promoting products. Not only buyers are a potential market, but sellers also compete through their products and published content. The influence of the current digital era has led to intense and competitive competition in the industrial world among businesses. Technology and information are currently experiencing rapid advancements, one of which is the development of internet technology. This situation requires businesses to utilize digital tools in their operations. Failure to keep up with the current digital era will certainly leave their businesses behind. Promotion is one of the factors influencing purchasing decisions. Through promotion, a business can provide consumers with information about its products. Promotion through social media is a key requirement in today's world, as everyone relies on and cannot be separated from their smartphones. Promotion is currently effective using social media because businesses need effective marketing tools to expand their market share (Puspitarini & Nuraeni, 2019).

Promotion through TikTok is effective because the platform allows direct interaction with consumers, rapid information dissemination, and the ability to create engaging and shareable content. This makes TikTok a powerful tool in modern digital marketing strategies (Hartanto, 2023). Promotion through TikTok is considered a step for Acehese cake MSME sellers to introduce their products and attract consumer interest, by adapting to current trends and promotional variations. TikTok, a currently trending social media platform, is widely accessed. TikTok is an app for creating and sharing short, vertical videos. TikTok has 99.1 million active users in Indonesia. TikTok is used not only for entertainment but also as a platform for information seeking and business development. They can grow their businesses by sharing engaging promotions on the app.

The development of the TikTok application can indirectly become a strategic place for marketing a brand or product that can reach consumers and even interact directly with consumers. Marketers are required to always develop, currently marketing strategies through digital platforms or social media influence someone in making purchasing decisions. TikTok shows significant dominance in increasing purchasing decisions compared to other platforms due to several unique factors, namely because of its short and interesting content format, TikTok's highly personalized algorithm, seamless E-commerce integration, the power of influencer marketing, trends and virality and interaction and community. Although other platforms also have E-commerce and influencer marketing features,

the unique combination of an engaging content format, a strong personalized algorithm, seamless E-commerce integration, and a viral trend culture makes TikTok very effective in driving purchasing decisions. Product innovation is the process or result of developing ideas and utilizing existing products and resources to create greater value. Product innovation involves developing existing products by creating new ideas that offer innovative, satisfying products to consumers, attracting their attention amidst intense business competition (Diharto, 2022) . Product innovation means developing new products that meet consumer needs and desires, thus generating purchasing interest. This need can be realized through purchasing decisions. Product innovation must be able to build sustainable competitive advantage in a rapidly changing environment and move towards a global market. Successful product innovation requires a fit between the process and a supportive environment. (Permatasari and Maryana 2021). Product innovation also plays a crucial role in attracting consumer interest. Amidst intense competition, Acehese Cake MSMEs strive to deliver quality products while also meeting market needs and preferences. Innovation in formulation, packaging, and marketing is key to maintaining consumer appeal, particularly among the younger generation who are active on social media. A purchasing decision is the process an individual or group goes through to select, purchase, and use a product. This process is influenced by various factors, both internal factors such as needs, motivations, and attitudes, and external factors such as social, cultural, and advertising influences. This decision involves several stages that help consumers decide whether to purchase a product (Wicaksono et al., 2023) .

The purchasing decision process begins when consumers recognize a need or problem that needs to be addressed. This need can include purchasing a product to fulfill a daily need or an emotional need, such as purchasing a product to provide a sense of satisfaction or pride. After recognizing their need, consumers will begin searching for the necessary information to find the product that meets their need. Information sources can come from various sources, such as advertisements, social media, friends, family, or personal experiences. After making a purchase, consumers will evaluate whether their purchase decision was satisfactory. If consumers are satisfied, they are likely to become loyal customers and recommend the product to others (Tonce & Rangga, 2022) .

The large number of Acehese cake micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) that have entered digital marketing certainly want their businesses to grow, gain public recognition, achieve significant turnover, enhance their brand name, and continue to innovate to compete with competitors. On the other hand, each Acehese cake MSME plays a role in advancing the economy and reducing unemployment in Aceh. This certainly requires the community to switch to digital systems. Many Acehese cake MSMEs have emerged and are starting to promote their cakes on social media, including Instagram and TikTok. Acehese cake MSME culinary traders implement online ordering and delivery systems, collaborating with ordering applications. All of this can be seen from their advertising content and posts on Instagram and TikTok. The existence of Instagram and TikTok, which can reach a wide scope, has resulted in many buyers and the name of Acehese cake MSMEs is better known to the public. Posting content on Instagram and TikTok, as well as the consistency of MSME entrepreneurs who frequently advertise on Instagram and TikTok, also influences the public to make purchasing decisions. Based on this background, the researcher is interested in studying and conducting further research in the form of research entitled "The Influence of Promotion Through TikTok and Product Innovation on Purchasing Decisions in Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs".

1.2 Formulation of the problem

Based on the problem background above, the problem formulation in this research is as follows:

" How do promotions through TikTok and simultaneous product innovation influence purchasing decisions in Acehese Traditional Cake MSMEs?"

1.3 Research purposes

The purpose of this study is to test and analyze how promotions through TikTok and product innovation simultaneously influence purchasing decisions in Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs .

2. Literature Review

2.1 Buying decision

A purchasing decision is a thought process in which an individual evaluates various options and decides on a product from among many. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2020), a purchasing decision is the stage in the buyer decision-making process where the consumer actually makes a purchase. According to Agustina Rennie et al., 2023, a purchasing decision is a final decision made by a customer to purchase a service or product, taking into account a

number of specific considerations. Purchasing decisions made by customers reflect the extent to which marketers have marketed a product to customers .

2.2 Promotion Through TikTok

Kotler & Keller (2021) stated that social media, including TikTok, is an effective marketing tool because it is able to create direct interactions with consumers, increase engagement, and spread information virally at a relatively low cost. Chaffey & Smith (2022) stated that TikTok is a prime example of viral-based marketing where brands can grow rapidly through relatable and easily shareable content by users. Solomon, Marshall, & Stuart (2018) emphasized that TikTok creates a more personal experience for users, so marketing through this platform must be authentic and entertaining in order to increase consumer attraction and trust in a brand .

2.3 Product Innovation

Product innovation is an effort undertaken by a company or institution to create or update existing products with the aim of creating, improving, enhancing, and developing previously produced products to be better and have higher sales value (Safira, 2022) . Product innovation is the development of new products by a company, whether existing or not. Completely new replacement products or more modern, up-to-date developments of existing products can increase consumer desire in product purchasing decisions.

3. Research methods

3.1 Analysis Method and Hypothesis Testing Design

3.1.1 Analysis Method

The statistical test used in this study is multiple linear regression analysis, which is an analysis used to present data in numerical form. Based on the description that has been explained on the types of variables used, namely dependent variables and independent variables, the analysis used by the author is a type of multiple linear regression analysis using a statistical program tool, namely SPSS (*Statistical Package For The Social Sciences*). This study uses the multiple linear regression formula as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + e$$

Information :

Y : Purchase Decision

a : Constant

$b_1 - b_3$: Regression coefficient of each variable

X_1 : Promotion via Tiktok

X_2 : Product Innovation

e : *Standard Error*

3.1.2 Hypothesis Testing Design

➤ Preliminary Test (T-Test)

The T-test aims to determine the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The decision-making criteria in this study (Duwila et al., 2022) are: if the p-value is <0.05 , H_a is accepted. Conversely, if the p-value is ≥ 0.05 , H_a is rejected. The test criteria are:

H_{01} : Promotion through TikTok does not influence the purchasing decision of Acehese Typical Cake MSME products in Banda Aceh city.

H_{a1} : Promotion through TikTok influences the purchasing decision of Acehese Typical Cake MSME products in Banda Aceh city .

H_{02} : Product innovation does not influence the purchasing decision of Acehese Typical Cake MSME products in Banda Aceh city .

H_{a2} : Product innovation influences the purchasing decision of Acehese Typical Cake MSME products in Banda Aceh city .

➤ Simultaneous test (F test)

The F test aims to determine whether or not there is a simultaneous influence of independent variables on the dependent variable. The decision-making criteria in testing using the p-value or calculated F in research (Duwila et al., 2022) are: if the p-value <0.05 or calculated $F \geq F$ table, then H_a is accepted. Conversely, if the p-value ≥ 0.05 or calculated $F < F$ table, then H_a is rejected. The test criteria are:

- H₀₃ : Promotion through TikTok and product innovation do not influence the purchasing decision of Acehese Typical Cake MSME products in Banda Aceh city.
- H_{a3}: Promotion through TikTok and product innovation influence the purchasing decision of Acehese Typical Cake MSME products in Banda Aceh city.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Data Testing

test used in this study is the *Product Moment correlation technique* . Data is considered valid if the calculated r test results are greater than the table r .

The reliability test used is the *Cronbach's alpha analysis technique* . The test reliability value for the promotion variable through TikTok (X_1) is 0.835 , product innovation (X_2) is 0.918 , and purchasing decisions (Y) are 0.866. All variables in this research instrument have a test reliability value greater than the *Cronbach's alpha value* of 0.60. This means that the research questionnaire used meets the requirements. conditions or reliable .

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

Analysis regression linear multiple This used For know influence promotion via Tiktok (X_1) and product innovation (X_2) on purchasing decisions (Y) . Results analysis in study This can seen on table following:

Table 4.1
Results Analysis Regression Multiple
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
			Beta		
1 (Constant)	2,066	,749		2,758	,007
Total_Promotion_Through_Tiktok	,811	,070	,699	11,622	,000
Total Product Innovation	,300	,063	,286	4,753	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Total_Purchase_Decisions

Primary Data (2024)

Based on table 4.12 above, it can be seen that the output data from the multiple linear regression analysis analyzed using SPSS produces the following regression equation:

$$Y = 2,066 + 0,811 X_1 + 0,300 X_2 + e$$

Equality regression on own meaning as following:

- Mark Constant $b_a = 2.066$
Means if promotional variables via TikTok (X_1) , and product innovation (X_2) No changed or considered constant (worth 0), so average purchasing decision (Y) will worth 2,066. This means that purchasing decisions will be low if there is no promotion through Tiktik and product innovation.
- Coefficient regression $b_1 = 0.811$
Promotion via Tiktok (X_1) have coefficient regression with direction positive as big as 0,811 . Matter This means that every increase 1 unit on Promotion variable through TikTok (X_1) will cause purchasing decision variable (Y) go on of 0.811 units. This means that the more accessible the promotion via TikTok, the higher the purchase satisfaction.
- Regression coefficient $b_3 = 0.300$
Product innovation (X_2) has a positive regression coefficient of 0.300. Assuming other independent variables remain constant, this means that for every 1-unit increase in product innovation, purchasing decisions (Y) will increase by 0.300 units. This means that the higher the product innovation, the higher the purchasing satisfaction.

4.2.1 Test t (Partial)

Based on statistical calculations using the SPSS program as shown in the table above, the following results were obtained:

a. Promotion via Tiktok (X_1)

On Promotion variable through TikTok (X_1) is obtained $t_{count} (11,622) > t_{table} (1,986)$, so H_0 rejected (H_a accepted), This means that the promotion variable via TikTok (X_1) has an effect positive and significant impact on purchasing decisions (Y) on Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs in Banda Aceh city at a significance level of 5%. This means that the better the promotion via TikTok (X_1), the higher the purchasing decision (Y).

b. Product Innovation (X_2)

the product innovation variable (X_2) it is obtained mark $t_{count} (4,753) > t_{table} (1,986)$, so H_0 rejected (H_a accepted), meaning that the product innovation variable (X_3) has an effect positive and significant impact on purchasing decisions (Y) in Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs in Banda Aceh city, significance level 5%. This means that the better the product innovation (X_2), the higher the purchasing decision (Y) and vice versa.

4.2.2 Test F (Simultaneous)

Test F or simultaneous test done to find out the significance coefficient regression all over predictor (variable independent) in in model in a way simultaneously. So in this case testing significance influence promotion via Tiktok (X_1) and product innovation (X_2) simultaneously on purchasing decisions (Y).

Table 4.2
Results Test F (Simultaneous)
ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1016,514	2	508,257	507,479	,000 ^a
	Residual	93,142	93	1,002		
	Total	1109,656	95			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Total_Product_Innovation, Total_Promotion_Through_Tiktok

b. Dependent Variable: Total_Purchase_Decisions

Source: Primary data (2024)

Based on results calculation k statistic use SPSS Which stated on tab el above, obtained mark F_{count} amounting to $507,479 \geq F_{table}$ amounting to 3,094 with level significance 0.000. The resulting significance value is less than 0.05. This means that the purchasing decision variable (Y) can be significantly explained by promotions through TikTok (X_1) and product innovation (X_2). Thus, it can be concluded that the promotion variable through TikTok (X_1) and product innovation (X_2) simultaneously (together) or simultaneously have a significant influence on purchasing decisions (Y) at Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs in Banda Aceh City.

5 CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on the influence of promotions through TikTok and product innovation on purchasing decisions of Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs in Banda Aceh city, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. Promotion through TikTok has a partial positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions of Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs in Banda Aceh city.
2. Product innovation partially has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions at Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs in Banda Aceh city.
3. Promotion through TikTok and product innovation simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions at Acehese Typical Cake MSMEs in Banda Aceh city.

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